

DEVELOPMENT OF SELF-PROPELLED SOYBEAN HARVESTER

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Abstract

During the peak harvesting period shortage of skilled labour, higher cost consumed for harvesting, and time in harvesting are the major problems faced by farmers. In Vidarbha region of Maharashtra the soybean crop sown as intercrop is still harvested by manual labours which is costly and time consuming. To overcome these problems the present study was undertaken to develop the self-propelled soybean harvester to reduce the drudgery, time and cost of harvesting of soybean crop for marginal farmers. The machine consists of the various parts such as main frame, petrol engine, power transmission system, cutter bar, handle, crop deflector, ground wheels, isolator etc. The average shattering losses were found to be 8.99 g/m² (2.45 %). The average uncut losses were found to be 3.86 g/m² (0.61%). The average harvesting losses were observed to be 2.96 %. The cutting efficiency was observed as 100 percent at the forward speed of 2.51 km/h. The theoretical field capacity, effective field capacity and field efficiency were found as 0.215 ha/h, 0.1748 ha/h and 81.31 percent respectively. Fuel consumption of self-propelled soybean harvester was 0.714 lit/h.

Keywords: Soybean, soybean harvesting, harvesting losses.

Introduction

World soybean production in 2020-21 is estimated as 353.47 million tonnes from a total area of 136.82 million hectares. India ranks fourth in area with 12.12 million hectares (29.94 million acres) accounting for 8.86% of the world area and fifth in production with 11.23 million tonnes in 2020-21 (Anonymous, 2022). Soybean harvesting constitutes one of the most laborious and time-consuming operations of farming, it is done mainly with sickles, despite all its deficiencies. In the absence of suitable/improved harvesting equipment, manual harvesting is a cumbersome job and requires about 180 to 200 man-h/ha to harvest a crop. In Maharashtra soybean crop sown as intercrop with 4 rows of soybean in between 2 rows of Pigeon Pea and Cotton. The spacing of pigeon peas with four rows of soybeans is usually 2.25 meters, so it is not suitable for combinations during intercropping. The smallest combine harvester available in the market has a cutter bar size of 2.10 meters and a total width of it is 2.62 meters, which is impractical for intercropping operations. It restricts the use of combine harvesters in intercropping. Considerable quantity of labours required for harvesting crop by traditional method. Bending posture for hours to harvest crop may create health problems to the labours. Harvesting of soybean with a sickle involves repetitive movements, such as bending, squatting, and reaching. These actions can put strain on different parts of the body, particularly the back, shoulders, and knees. Thus, there is a need for a smaller and more efficient harvester which would be considerably cheaper and more accessible in intercropping and give the alternative to reduce the drudgery of workers at the time of harvesting.

To overcome all the problems, present study conducted to develop self-propelled soybean harvester. The experiment was conducted in Department of Farm Power and Machinery, Dr. PDKV, Akola.

Material and Methods**Table 1. Specifications of self-propelled soybean harvester**

Parameters	Specifications
Overall dimensions, mm	
Length × width × height	1400 × 800 × 1000
Cutting unit	
Type of cutter bar	Reciprocating knife section
Length of cutter bar, mm	750
Knife section	Standard
Type	Trapezoidal
Blade	Serrated
Pitch of cutter bar, mm	50
Ground wheel	
Type	Rubber tube wheels
Diameter, mm	669
Handle grip diameter, mm	30
Width of cutter bar, mm	800
Power transmission for cutting mechanism	

Functional components of Self-propelled soybean harvester:**Engine**

A petrol engine was provided as a source of power to self-propelled soybean harvester. The power required for the performance of harvester 0.25 Hp, petrol engine of 1.5 Hp was selected as a power source.

Power transmission system

The pulley of diameter 2.5 inch and 7 inch was mounted on the engine shaft and crank shaft respectively. For transmitting the power, the V-belt is used. The bell crank mechanism was used to convert the linear motion of cutter bar to reciprocating motion. First small pulley mounted on engine shaft and large pulley was mounted on shaft connected to bell crank mechanism. Power is transmitted to ground wheels through combination of belt and chain drive mechanism. A gear box was added to transmit power from pulley to ground wheels. Gearbox transmit power from a belt and pulley drive mechanism to a chain and sprocket mechanism.

Handle

The handle made of mild steel pipe of 25 mm diameter was mounted on rear part of the main frame. The length and height of handle were 850 mm and 1000 mm, respectively and the diameter of handle grip was 30 mm.

Cutter bar

The cutter bar of length 800 mm was used for cutting of two rows of soybean. A reciprocating type cutter bar having standard knife section of 50 mm stroke length and two cuts per stroke was used. The cutter bar of trapezoidal shape with serrated blades used in harvester.

Crop deflector

A crop deflector is typically a shield located in front of the cutter bar. It helps to direct the standing crop towards the cutter bar, ensuring that the crop enters the cutting platform smoothly and uniformly.

Type	Belt and pulley arrangement
Driven pulley, mm	180
Driving pulley, mm	60

Isolator

Machine vibrations were high because of reciprocating motion of cutter bar. To reduce handle vibrations, an isolator was placed at the interface of the handlebar and metal plate. Isolator breaks the contact between two metallic surfaces and reduces the handle vibrations effectively. Its material is isobutyl rubber and stainless steel.

Result And Discussion

The field performance of self-propelled soybean harvester was conducted on PDKV AMBA 100-39 variety of soybean in the research field at Dr. PDKV, Akola. The overall performance of the machine was

Table 2. Crop parameters of soybean

Sr. No.	Parameters	Average Values*
1.	Crop height, mm	571.95
2.	Row to row spacing, mm	450
3.	Plant to plant spacing, mm	89
4.	Minimum pod height from ground surface, mm	111.17
5.	Stem diameter, mm	7.23
6.	Plant population, plants per m ²	41
7.	Pre harvest loss, %	1.37
8.	Moisture content (stem), % db	29.61
9.	Moisture content (grain), %	16.45
10.	Stubble height, mm	107.6

Harvesting losses

Losses occurred during the harvesting of crop are called as harvesting losses. Total harvesting losses include the pre harvest losses, shattering losses and uncut losses. Harvesting losses measured in 5 plots of 1 m² area. The results obtained for harvesting losses were shown in Table 3. The percentage of harvest losses were determined by the equation below,

$$H = \frac{Wgt - Wg1}{Yg} \times 100$$

Where,

Yg - Grain Yield (g/m²)

Wgt - Total Losses (g/m²)

Wg1 - Pre-Harvest Losses (g/m²)

Table 3. Percentage of harvesting losses

Sr. No		P ₁	P ₂	P ₃	P ₄	P ₅	Average
Grain yield, g/m ²		856.3	644.34	664.32	514.66	587.82	653.48
Pre harvest losses	g/m ²	15.12	13.54	4.52	8.31	3.47	8.99
	%	1.76	2.10	0.68	1.61	0.63	1.37
Shattering losses	g/m ²	15.39	15.09	13.61	17.02	16.38	15.49
	%	1.79	2.34	2.04	3.30	2.78	2.45
Uncut losses	g/m ²	1.87	4.82	5.09	2.43	5.22	3.86
	%	0.21	0.74	0.76	0.47	0.88	0.61
Harvesting losses	g/m ²	17.26	19.91	18.7	19.45	21.6	19.35
	%	2.01	3.08	2.81	3.77	3.67	2.96

Cutting efficiency

Cutting efficiency of the machine is the percentage of number of plants cut from total number of plants present per m². No uncut plants were observed in field, therefore cutting efficiency is 100 %.

Effective working width

The working width of the developed machine is the distance between 2 rows as the machine was able to cut 2 rows of soybean crop spaced at a distance of 450 mm. The effective working width or cutting width of the machine was found to be 900 mm.

Theoretical field capacity

The theoretical field capacity of self-propelled soybean harvester was determined by using following equation which was found to be 0.215 ha/h.

$$T.F.C, \text{ ha/h} = \frac{S(\text{Speed of operation, } \frac{\text{km}}{\text{h}}) \times W(\text{Width of operation, m})}{10}$$

Effective field capacity

The effective field capacity of self-propelled soybean harvester was time consumed for actual work and lost for other activities such as turning and break downs. The time required for harvesting 1 hectare

area of the field was found as 5.721 hours and effective field capacity was found as 0.1748 ha/h.

Field efficiency

The field efficiency of self-propelled soybean harvester was determined by taking the ratio of effective field capacity to theoretical field capacity. It was found as 81.31 per cent.

Fuel consumption

The fuel required for harvesting 1 hectare area of the field was found as 4.086 lit/ha.

Conclusion

Average shattering losses and uncut losses were found 2.45 % and 0.61% respectively. The average harvesting losses were observed to be 2.96 %.

The theoretical field capacity, effective field capacity, field efficiency and cutting efficiency were found as 0.215 ha/h, 0.1748 ha/h and 81.31 %, 100% respectively.

The effective field capacity was found as 0.1748 ha/h which is higher than traditional method of harvesting.

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